

PLA-PEG-Cholesterol Biomimetic Membrane for Electrochemical Sensing of Antioxidants

*Ahmed H. M. Mohammed-Sadhakathullah,^{a,b} Sofia Paulo-Mirasol,^{a,b}
Brenda G. Molina,^{a,b,c} Juan Torras,^{a,b*} and Elaine Armelin,^{a,b*}*

^{a)} Innovation in Materials and Molecular Engineering-Biomaterials for Regenerative Therapies (IMEM-BRT) Group - Departament of Chemical Engineering - Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) C/ d'Eduard Maristany, 10-14, Building I, 2nd floor - 08019 - Barcelona (Spain)

^{b)} Barcelona Research Centre for Multiscale Science and Engineering - Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC) - C/ d'Eduard Maristany, 10-14, Building I, basement - 08019 - Barcelona (Spain)

^{c)} Institute for Bioengineering of Catalonia (IBEC), The Barcelona Institute of Science and Technology, Baldiri Reixac 10-12, 08028 Barcelona (Spain)

*Corresponding author: elaine.armelin@upc.edu and joan.torras@upc.edu

ABSTRACT

Polymeric membranes exhibit unique and modulate transport properties when they are properly functionalised, which make them ideal for ions transport, molecules separation and molecules interactions. The present work proposes the design and fabrication of nanostructured membranes, composed by biodegradable poly(lactic acid) (PLA) and poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG), incorporating a lipophilic molecule (cholesterol) covalently bonded, were especially designed to provide even more application opportunities in sensors field. Electrochemical studies, by means of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS), cyclic voltammetry (CV) and square wave voltammetry (SWV), revealed important differences regarding the functionalised and non-functionalised PLA systems. PEG-cholesterol building block units showed a clear affinity with ascorbic acid (vitamin C) and Trolox[®] (a water-soluble analogue of vitamin E), both hydrophilic in nature, with a limit of detection capacity of 8.12 μM for AA and 3.53 μM for AA and Trolox, respectively, in aqueous salt solution. The bioinspired polymer may be used to incorporate antioxidant property that allow the design of anti-stress biosensors, electrodes for the detection of vitamin C or vitamin E in biomedical nutrition programs, among other applications.

Keywords: poly(lactic acid), poly(ethyleneglycol), cholesterol, nanomembranes, antioxidant molecules, electrochemical detection.

1. Introduction

The strategical design of bioinspired membranes (BMs), *i.e.* membranes that contain non-biological and biological molecules, to provide enhanced ions transport rates or mediated molecules separations has proved applied applications in several fields.[1,2] Particularly, in the biomedical area, hybrid systems have attracted attention due to the achievement of some relevant properties of the new material, making them suitable to be in contact with biological fluids and living organisms.[3–7] Mano and co-workers,[8] for example, developed a hybrid biologically-inspired adhesive patch, composed by natural polymers (chitosan, alginate and hyaluronic acid) and dopamine as outer layer, obtaining a free-standing multilayered membrane for skin wound healing. The new adhesive showed increased human fibroblast cell viability and selective bacteriostatic activity against *Escherichia coli* but not against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Another example is the work reported by Lin *et al.* [9] with the application of BMs as an electronic sensor patch, composed by a nanoporous membrane (essentially inorganic-organic hybrid compound), for long-term noninvasive monitoring of glucose, by enzymatic conversion. In the last years, various smart devices, based in BM, have been developed for non-invasive health monitoring and sensor detection.[10–14]

However, in modern invasive treatments, such as cancer therapy, immunotherapies, ocular drug-delivery, implantable sensors, among other examples; BMs are envisaged to be made with fully bioresorbable materials and to ensure the non-toxic effect of the clinical degraded and excreted products.[15–19] In this sense, synthetic biodegradable polymers are the ideal candidates for membranes fabrication, due to the controlled purity of the raw materials used to prepare them and, moreover, as a result of the controlled purification of the final product (*i.e.* free of by-products or undesirable molecules). The most employed synthetic bioresorbable polymers are: poly(lactic

acid) (PLA); poly(L-lactic acid) (PLLA); poly(glycolic acid) (PGA); poly(L-lactide-co-glycolide) (PLLGA); poly(caprolactone) (PCL); polyurethane (PU); and hydrogels made with poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG).[20]

Furthermore, some of the abovementioned polymers can be obtained from renewable sources, as is the case of lactic acid (LA), precursor of PLA (D,L-heterochiral), PLLA (L-homochiral); which can be isolated from corn and cassava, among other carbohydrates.[21] On the other side, bio-PCL can be prepared from the chemical conversion of saccharides to ethanol and acetic acid, and later, ethanol is transformed to cyclohexanone by oxidation reactions.[22] Besides being bioabsorbable, those polymers are biocompatible and FDA approved for *in vivo* systems, being extensively explored in clinical uses.[23–25] In terms of membrane applications, PLA also combines excellent nanofiltration and separation physical performances,[2,26–28] which convert this polymer in an ideal polymer matrix support for other functional molecules.

Among the current strategies for BM fabrication, Kumar and co-workers[1] have recently compiled the principals, emphasizing in the importance of the fabrication method and the uniform pores distribution for the final application envisaged. Therefore, in organic solvent nanofiltrations, for example, biological membrane proteins (MPs) and artificial water channels (AWCs), used to induce pores formation, have some limitations. In another work,[29] the same authors found an interesting synergy for the selective membrane ions transport and permselectivity, by combining a synthetic lamellar block copolymer as matrix (hydrophilic and hydrophobic structure), with artificial peptide-appended pillar[5]arene (PAP5) and natural (gramicidin A) model channels.

Inspired by the current state-of-art in BMs technology, in this work we report the preparation and the performance of a synthetic nanomembrane, based on bioresorbable and biocompatible PLA matrix and PEG-cholesterol building block units, for the detection of L-ascorbic acid (or

vitamin C) and 6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid (or Trolox[®]), a derivative compound from vitamin E. Those molecules were chosen as typical representatives of hydrophilic antioxidant molecules and due to their important role in body fluids. The solid-supported nanomembrane preparation only involves one surface activation and two steps of synthesis, without the need of exhaustive sample purification or long drying time processes. The success of the PLA-PEG-Chol covalent bonding was achieved by cold-plasma surface activation. The chemical structure was proved by spectroscopy analysis, whereas the membrane resistance and the sensor sensibility towards the antioxidants molecules were evaluated by electrochemical techniques.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

PLA, a Natureworks product, was kindly supplied by Nupik International (Polinyà, Spain) (polymer 2002D). As stated by the manufacturer, this PLA's D content is 4.25%, its residual monomer content is 0.3%, its density is 1.24 g/cc, its glass transition temperature (T_g) is 58 °C, and its melting point is 153 °C. According to gel permeation chromatography (GPC) analysis, the polydispersity index and average molecular weights were $M_n = 98,100 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $M_w = 181,000 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, and 1.85, respectively. L-Ascorbic acid (99 %, white powder); (R)-(+)-6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid (98 %, white powder, Trolox[®] comercial trademark); poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) (87–89% hydrolysed, M_w 13.000–23.000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), *N*-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-*N'*-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride, *N*-hydroxysuccinimide, phosphate buffer saline were purchased from Sigma–Aldrich (Spain). 1,1,1,3,3,3-Hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP) was purchased from Apollo Scientific Limit (UK). Cholesterol-PEG-NH₂ (Purity: $\geq 95\%$)

was purchased from Abbexa (UK). Indium tin oxide (ITO)-coated square samples of $10 \times 10 \text{ mm}^2$ of size were cut from ITO-coated boro-aluminosilicate glass slides with surface resistivity of 5-15 Ω/sq (Sigma-Aldrich, 576360, Spain).

2.2. Fabrication of PLA Nanomembranes (PLA NMs)

The PLA NMs were fabricated over ITO/glass substrates, by modulating the spin-coater speed rate and time. For it, separated stock solutions of 10 mg mL^{-1} of PLA and 10 mg mL^{-1} of PVA in 1,1,1,3,3,3-hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP), were prepared. Then, two different compositions of PLA and PVA were blended in a 90:10 and 99:1 v/v (PLA: PVA) ratios. Those new solutions were mixed for 1 hour and filtered to discard possible aggregates before the spin-coating process. The blend polymer solutions were spin coated at speeds of 600, 1200 and 2500 rpm for 30 and 60 s, using a WS-400B-NPP single water spin processor (Laurell Technologies Co.). Finally, the films adhered to the ITO substrates were immersed in milliQ water overnight to dissolve PVA domains and to create the pores. The PLA nanomembranes deposited onto ITO were physical-chemical characterized and the average thicknesses of the films and the pore-size distribution were measured by atomic force microscopy (AFM). A simplified illustration of the whole process is depicted in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. a) Schematic representation of the dissolution of the PLA and PVA polymers in HFIP, and the following mixture of the appropriate amount of both solubilized polymers in a Vortex mixer. b) Deposition of the PLA:PVA solution on ITO/glass substrate and spin coater to the desired speed and time. The ITO/PLA:PVA slides are then placed to a Petri dish containing water and left overnight for the dissolution of PVA molecules and, subsequent pores creation.

2.3. Functionalization of the PLA NMs with PEG-Cholesterol building block

The functionalization of the PLA NMs with PEG-Cholesterol molecules was performed in only three steps. First step is the surface activation of the membrane by using oxygen-plasma (O₂-plasma) to create polar reactive groups (-COOH, -COO⁻, and radicals) on the polymer surface. PLA NMs were placed in a 2.6 dm³ chamber, which was vacuum-purged and filled with oxygen gas. More specifically, the system was evacuated until the specified pumping down pressure (0.2 mbar) was obtained, which corresponded to the final pressure of the purging stage prior to applying

the electric discharge. Next, the PLA surfaces were exposed to an electric discharge with a maximum power output of 300 W using a power source. The gas pressure was set at 0.8 mbar, with a minimum gas flux of ~ 15 sccm, and the final pressure was automatically controlled by a valve. For such step, the power supply was fixed to 30 W and 100 W, both with a maximum time of exposure of 2 min each.

In the second step, the surface activated PLA NMs were immediately transferred to a Petri dish containing *N*-(3-dimethylaminopropyl)-*N'*-ethylcarbodiimide (EDC) and *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) with concentrations of 0.1M and 0.2 M, respectively, in phosphate buffered saline solution (PBS; pH 7.4) to create the amine reactive coupling groups on PLA surfaces. The carboxyl groups generated on the PLA surface, activated by oxygen plasma, reacted with EDC/NHS and led to the formation of NHS ester groups. These groups, by transamidation reaction, further react with the amine groups of other molecules, as is the case of H₂N-PEG-Cholesterol molecules, to obtain the amide linkage represented in the Scheme 2. For this third step, the samples were first cleaned with milliQ water in order to get rid of any unreacted NHS and EDC molecules. The transamidation of NHS moiety was used to link the PEG-Cholesterol building block to the PLA NM. The H₂N-PEG-Cholesterol (1 mg·ml⁻¹ of PBS) solution was added to the PLA samples and allowed to react for 4 hours before being rinsed to eliminate any unreactive molecules (hereafter denoted as PLA-PEG-Chol, for simplification). The complete procedure can be seen in Scheme 2.

Additionally to the NMs preparation, thick and macroscopic PLA- and PLA-PEG-Chol films (non-perforated) were prepared for the chemical structure characterization of the samples by spectroscopy tools. The procedure was similar to the abovementioned synthesis, without PVA sacrificial polymer. Briefly, PLA was dissolved in CH₂Cl₂ (1% w/v-10 mg·mL⁻¹) and was poured into teflon plates, afterwards, the sample was moved to the hood for the solvent evaporation and

film obtaining.[30] For the PLA film functionalization with NH₂-PEG-Chol molecules, the procedure was the same than that reported in the section 2.3. Both samples were left in the desiccator under vacuum for complete drying (overnight). An average thickness of 21.4 ± 2.2 μm was obtained for the macroscopic films (Figure S1).

Scheme 2. Synthetic route to solid-supported functionalization of PLA NMs and subsequent covalent bonding with NH₂-PEG-Cholesterol building block units.

2.4. Characterization of PLA-PEG-Cholesterol NMs

The chemical structures of PLA and PLA-PEG-Chol films were confirmed by FTIR and ¹H-NMR spectroscopies. Due to the nanometric thickness of the films, it was unpractical to perform the chemical characterization of the NM samples. Therefore, it was carried out with the thicker films described in the section above. A Thermo-Fisher Nicolet 6700 FTIR spectrometer, equipped with Smart SAGA (specular aperture grazing angle, with an incidence angle of 80° from the normal surface and an aperture window of 16 mm) and with ATR-Smart Orbit (attenuated total reflectance

with ZnSe crystal window) accessories. Gold reflecting optic slide was employed as background spectrum in SAGA reflectance mode. Omnic software was used to fix the parameters of scan and to process the data. All spectra were recorded in a wavenumber range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} and 64 accumulation scans. The PLA and PLA-PEG-Chol H-NMR spectra were obtained by using a Bruker NMR Ascend 400 of 400MHz spectrometer. For each sample, 64 scans were performed using a sweep with of 8 MHz. Final spectra were analysed using Topspin software. To confirm the previous results, fresh-prepared nanomembranes were evaluated by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) with an XPS equipment from SPECS XPS System. The instrument operates with a XR50 Al anode (150 W, 10 kV), with a hemispherical analyzer Phoibos 150 and an electron detector MCD-9. The working pressure was maintained below 5×10^{-8} mbar. High resolution XPS spectra were acquired by Gaussian/Lorentzian curve, fitting after S shape background subtraction, for the following elements: C 1s, O 1s, and N 1s. The data were analysed with Casa XPS software (Version 2.3.19PR1.0) and all the spectra were calibrated with respect to the binding energy of the carbon C1s peak (284.8 eV).

Water contact angle (WCA) measurements were carried out with the sessile drop method at room temperature. Images of milli-Q water drops (0.9 μL) were recorded after stabilization (10 s) with an OCA 15EC instrument (Data-Physics Instruments GmbH, Filderstadt) and analysed using the SCA20 software. For each sample, the average WCA value and the corresponding standard deviation were derived from ten independent measures at least. The WCA was also monitored during 10 minutes to determine the membrane ability to absorb the water droplet, since the sensor is intended to be permeable to water.

Topographical changes induced by the effect of spin-coater speed rate and time, as well as the effect of O_2 -plasma, in the preparation of PLA NMs were analysed by atomic force microscopy

(AFM). Therefore, the topographic images of the films were conducted with silicon TAP 150-G probes (Budget Sensors, Bulgaria), with a frequency of 150 kHz, and a force constant of 5 N m^{-1} , in tapping mode. Images were obtained with an AFM Dimension microscope (Bruker) using a NanoScope IV controller, under ambient conditions. The row scanning frequency was set at 1 Hz and the tip motion speed was $10 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. The surface roughness was quantified from the topographical images using the root mean square (RMS) roughness (R_q) parameter, which is considered to be more sensitive than the average roughness (R_a) for large deviations from the mean line/plane. The specific profile sections of the 2D and 3D AFM images were determined using the statistics application tools of the NanoScope Analysis software. The scan window size was $25 \times 25 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$. The NM thicknesses were estimated by the average of the pore depths measured with the NanoScope analysis software, in the cross-section areas. All values are inserted in Table 1.

Detailed inspection of morphology of the films, before and after functionalization, was conducted by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). A Focus Ion Beam Zeiss Neon 40 instrument (Carl Zeiss, Germany) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy system and operating at 5 kV was employed. NMs supported onto ITO/glass substrates were mounted on a double-sided adhesive carbon disc and were sputter-coated to prevent sample charging. The diameter of the pores, before and after functionalization with NH_2 -PEG-Cholesterol, was measured with the Image J software by applying the procedure described elsewhere.[31]

2.5. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS)

EIS measurements were performed by using a conventional three-electrode cell and an AUTOLAB-302N potentiostat/galvanostat, operating with sinusoidal voltage of 10 mV of amplitude within a frequency range between 10^5 Hz and 1 Hz. All experiments were performed at

room temperature with the perforated nanomembranes deposited onto ITO substrate, according to the procedure described in section 2.2. The NMs supported in ITO/glass substrates were used as working-electrode (WE, area of 0.6 cm²), Pt wire was used as counter-electrode (CE), and Ag|AgCl (KCl 3M) was employed as the reference electrode (RE). The electrolyte used was NaCl (0.1 M). After data collection, EIS results were then processed and fitted to an electrical equivalent circuit (EEC) by using Nova software. The samples analysed are: ITO/glass (blank sample), ITO/PLA perforated NMs and ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol.

2.6. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and square wave voltammetry (SWV) for the detection of hydrophilic and lipophilic antioxidants

The Autolab PGSTAT302N and NOVA software were used to perform cyclic voltammetry (CV) and square wave voltammetry (SWV) for the purpose of detecting antioxidants. The prepared samples on ITO-glass were used as working electrodes (WE) in experiments carried out at room temperature in a three-electrode cell filled with an aqueous 0.1 M lithium perchlorate (LiClO₄)/0.1 M potassium chloride (KCl) solution. Stainless steel (AISI 304) regularly served as the counter electrode (CE), and an Ag|AgCl electrode ($E^0 = 0.222$ V at 25 °) with a KCl 3M aqueous solution was used as the reference electrode (RE). For CV, the initial and final potential were -0.20 V, and the reverse potential was +1.10 V with a scan rate of 50 mV·s⁻¹. SWV voltammograms were recorded from 0–1.1 V at a scan rate of 50 mV·s⁻¹ and fixing an amplitude of 25 mV and a frequency of 10 Hz. Stock solutions of 0.1 M ascorbic acid (AA) and Trolox[®] (Tx) were prepared with distilled water and ethanol, respectively. The Trolox stock solutions were further diluted to 0.001 M using the electrolyte solution of H₂O:ethanol (7:3 v/v), due to solubility concerns of this compound in water.[32] All the solutions were bubbled with pure nitrogen gas during 5 min, before tests. During measurements, the electrolyte medium was placed in an ice bath, while various

antioxidant concentrations (1 μM , 5 μM , 10 μM , 25 μM , 50 μM , 100 μM , 150 μM and 200 μM) were added.

The choice of $\text{LiClO}_4/\text{KCl}$ salts as electrolyte in CV and SWV experiments were adopted due to: (i) the proved stability of $\text{LiClO}_4/\text{KCl}$ mixtures and good diffusion in neutral solutions for CV and SWV tests, and (ii) the relatively higher solubility of the analytes (AA and Trolox) in solutions containing a small amount of alcohol, compatible with the electrolyte. In summary, $\text{LiClO}_4/\text{KCl}$ was used to enhance the conductivity of the electrolyte at room temperature for the sensing applications and NaCl aqueous solution is typically reported to evaluate the electrical permittivity of the modified electrodes, when the working electrode is resistant to localized corrosion caused by chlorine ions.

2.7. LOD method validation

For quantification, linear regression analysis was used to evaluate the limit of detection (LOD). It was determined by the Equation 1:[33]

$$LOD = \frac{3S_b}{m}$$

where S_b is the standard deviation of the response or standard deviation of y -intercepts and m is the slope of the corresponding calibration curve. At least three SWV was run for each antioxidant molecule.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. PLA functionalization with PEG-Cholesterol building block molecules

The critical step of the NM fabrication was the functionalization of the PLA NMs with NH_2 -PEG-Chol building block molecules. Due to the nanometric thickness of the films and the nanometric layer of the functionalised samples, it was unpractical to perform the structural

characterization with the NMs. Therefore, to prove the success of the synthetic route, macrofilms were produced (Figure S1, supporting file) and characterized by FTIR, employing the same film preparation as reported in section 2.3 (film thickness $\sim 20 \mu\text{m}$). Two different accessories were necessary for the correct identification of the absorption bands. Figure 1a represents the spectra obtained from ATR-ZnSe reflectance, which offers unappreciable noise signals if compared to SAGA reflectance spectra (Figure 1b), but with a lower sensitivity to certain absorption bands, vibration modes and terminal groups than SAGA. Therefore, significant differences were found (Table S1). The PLA absorption bands were well distinguished by either ATR-reflectance or SAGA-reflectance spectra, whereas the presence of PEG-Chol and the amide covalent bonding with PLA was better identified with SAGA. The reason is that the grazing angle and the broad sliding aperture of the incidence beam in SAGA is more sensitive for sampling monolayer thin coatings. Moreover, in PLA film, OH bonds, from alcohol, and COOH terminal groups (3503 cm^{-1} and 3200 cm^{-1} , respectively), were also identified together with other stretching bands that appear more intense in SAGA spectrum than with ATR (as for example, CH_3 at 2992 cm^{-1} , in Figure 1a, if compared to the same band in Figure 1b). Furthermore, carbonyl band has been duplicated due to the presence of the ester group and the terminal acid groups (1738 and 1783 cm^{-1} , respectively), as shown.[34,35]

PLA-PEG-Chol FTIR spectrum presents absorption bands from both polymers and from cholesterol units.[36–38] Regarding amide-PEG-Chol linkages, the presence of NH groups from amide A linkages appears at 3280 cm^{-1} and 3140 cm^{-1} (hydrogen bonded and non-hydrogen bonded, respectively) and at 1581 cm^{-1} (Amide II), only observed with SAGA accessory (Figure 1b). Further and more important, the disappearance of OH from terminal acid groups in PLA matrix is clearly observed in the spectrum of PLA-PEG-Chol. Although such absorption bands can

be confused with SAGA noise (as that observed in the region of 2700-1800 cm^{-1}), the higher amount of PEG-Chol in twice-folded films confirmed that such bands increase, whereas noise did not. Therefore, they cannot be attributed to noise. In the C-H stretching absorbance zone, the appearance of $-\text{CH}_2-$ groups as sharp peaks at 2920 cm^{-1} and 2852 cm^{-1} can only be attributed to PEG and cholesterol entities and are observed either with ATR-ZnSe accessory (Figure 1a) or with SAGA (Figure 1b). Overtones of C-H rocking also appear as strong bands in the region of 980-850 cm^{-1} . The amide and urethane groups were hardly observed with ATR, but could be detected with SAGA, at $\sim 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, 1700 cm^{-1} (overlapped with C=O ester bands), and at 1580 cm^{-1} . Table S1 summarizes the main absorption bands and organic groups found and Figure S2 shows the two accessories used in the analyses.

The covalent bonding of the building block molecules was also proved by $^1\text{H-NMR}$, by comparing the spectra of both films solubilized in CDCl_3 solvent (Figure S3). In PLA sample (Figure S3a), there are only two sets of protons, one related to the quadruplet of CH bonds and one related to the duplet of CH_3 groups. In Figure S3b, the contribution of the PEG-Chol was only evidenced by the appearance of CH_2 peak at 3.64 ppm (inset image), most from PEG repeating units.[36]

To further support the proper functionalization of PLA NMs surfaces with PEG-Chol molecules, XPS analysis was carried out. The survey spectra of these materials are depicted in Figure 1c, and the atomic compositions are presented in Table S2. The survey spectra of both samples exhibit the presence of carbon (C1s peak at 285 eV) and oxygen (O1s peak at 533 eV). The amide bonds of the PEG-Chol linkage have been linked to the presence of nitrogen (N1s peak at 400 eV) in the case of PLA-PEG-Chol. Figure 1c also illustrates the deconvolution process applied to the C1s and O1s peaks observed in the high-resolution spectra obtained from the samples under

investigation. The C 1s peak was deconvoluted, resulting in the identification of three Gaussian curves. These curves were assigned to the presence of C-C bonds (284.8 eV), C-O bonds (286.45 eV), and O-C=O bonds (288.76 eV). In the case of PLA, the proportion of various bonds, as indicated by percentages in Table S2, was found to be significantly larger for C-C (44.4%) compared to C-O (29.14%) and O-C=O (26.5%).

Following functionalization, a significant rise in the percentage of C-O bonds (38.29%) is observed, accompanied by a modest decrease in the quantity of O-C=O bonds (21.59%). This phenomenon can be attributed to the introduction of linkages from the PEG units. An identical pattern is evident in the O1s components, wherein the proportion of C=O decreases from 26.9% to 72.73% following functionalization, while the proportion of O-C=O increases from 73.1% to 27.27%. The rise in the number of C=O bonds is ascribed to the incorporation of urethane moieties.

The high resolution N 1s peak of PLA-PEG-Chol demonstrates the presence of a varied environment for N atoms within an amide linkage. Specifically, it reveals the existence of N-H group at 399.45 eV (75.45%) and a bond with a neighbouring carbonyl group (N-C=O) at 402.01 eV (24.55%).

The results obtained from the ¹H-NMR, FTIR and XPS confirm that the PLA surface was successfully bonded with NH₂-PEG-Chol by using the PLA surface activation with cold-plasma and the transamidation synthetic route with EDC/NHS. Then, PLA nanomembranes were prepared over ITO/glass substrates and characterized after the induced physical perforation.

Figure 1. (a-b) Infrared spectra showing the main absorption bands of PLA and PLA-PEG-Chol films, in the range of 4000-600 cm^{-1} , obtained with two different accessories: (a) ATR-ZnSe crystal window, and (b) Specular Aperture Grazing Angle (SAGA) window, both in reflectance mode. For a), air was used as background to subtract the sample spectra, whereas in SAGA a gold specular support was used. c) Survey- and high-resolution spectra (C 1s, O 1s and N 1s) of PLA and chemically modified PLA-PEG-Chol films.

3.2. Fabrication of Perforated PLA Nanomembrane by Spin-Coater Optimized Process

Several samples of perforated nanomembrane were fabricated and characterized by 2D and 3D AFM, varying the PVA concentration as well as the spin coater parameters, in order to study the morphology and distribution of the pores through the films.

As can be seen in Table 1 and Figure 2, the concentration of PVA, which is used as the sacrificial polymer, is the major factor that determines the pore sizes of the PLA NMs.[27,39] Hence, 99:1

NMs (Figure 2a-c, 2D-height images) had smaller pores compared to 90:10 NMs (Figures 2d and S3). At a speed of 1200 rpm and 30 s of time, the pore sizes of 99:1 PLA:PVA NM were found to be 190 ± 71 nm; whereas it was 247 ± 85 nm for 90:10 composition, at the same set of conditions. Taking into account the homogenous distribution and pore size achieved with a concentration of PLA:PVA 99:1, with a speed rate of 1200 rpm and spin time of 30 s; such conditions were fixed as the most reproducible parameters for the preparation of the perforated PLA NMs.

With higher rotational speed (1200 rpm) and higher content of PVA molecules (90:10), the pore size increase substantially and are not homogenous (Figure S4), great standard deviation appears (Table 1). Therefore, we discarded to use this formulation for the application study envisaged in the present work, *i.e.* the use of PLA-PEG-Chol BMs as an electrochemical sensor of antioxidant molecules.

Table 1. Values of film thickness, roughness (Rq) and pore size distribution in the preparation of PLA nanoporated membranes as a function of spin-coater rotational speed and time.

PLA:PVA ratio	Rotational speed (rpm)	Spin time (s)	Thickness (nm)	Roughness (nm)	Pore size (nm)
99:1	2500	60	153 ± 7	42.9 ± 1.8	153 ± 67
		30	76 ± 7	19.7 ± 1.9	159 ± 71
99:1	1200	60	110 ± 9	12.6 ± 0.7	144 ± 66
		30	117 ± 13	44.8 ± 3.8	190 ± 71
90:10	1200	60	204 ± 22	69.1 ± 3.6	1139 ± 503
		30	184 ± 13	73.5 ± 4.7	247 ± 85

Figure 2. AFM images of perforated PLA NMs obtained with the following conditions: (a) PLA:PVA 99:1, speed: 2500 rpm, time: 60 s; (b) PLA:PVA 99:1, speed: 2500 rpm, time: 30 s; (c) PLA:PVA 99:1, speed: 1200 rpm, time: 30 s; (d) PLA:PVA 90:10, speed: 1200 rpm, time: 30 s. (a-d) 2D-Height AFM images. (e-h) 3D AFM images ($25 \times 25 \mu\text{m}^2$) of NMs with the same compositions and conditions described for 2D-height images (above).

3.3. Effect of O₂-Plasma Treatment on the Morphology of PLA NMs

The need to create a bilayer system with the covalent bond of the lipophilic molecules PEG-Chol, led us to apply a cold-plasma treatment to the perforated PLA NMs. The successful of this route approach (Scheme 2) was proved with macrofilms (Figure S1) prepared following the same procedure, with exception of the addition of PVA sacrificial polymer, which was also described by our group by using other polymer substrates, such as polyethylene[40,41] and polypropylene.[42,43] Despite mild conditions were applied the activated surface showed some changes on its morphology and wettability.

The surface wettability of the PLA NMs was assessed by water contact angle measurements, before and after the surface activation with O₂-plasma. Results indicate that the hydrophilicity of

the films increased ($73.1 \pm 3.4^\circ$ and $54.32 \pm 3.35^\circ$, before and after plasma treatment, respectively), due to the presence of more polar groups, such as carboxyl groups and radicals, exemplified in the Scheme 2.

Morphology changes of the membrane surface, before and after functionalization, were studied using AFM (Figure 3). Topographical analysis revealed that the surface roughness (R_q) increased greatly after the surface activation with O_2 -plasma. For PLA:PVA 99:1 NMs R_q values enhanced from 44.8 ± 3.8 nm to 122.8 ± 4.2 nm, before and after plasma treatment, respectively. Figure 3 shows the 2D- and 3D-AFM images of samples activated with a power intensity of 10 % and 30 W. As can be seen in the 3D images (Figure 3d), the surface is smoothness before plasma activation and became randomly peaked and sharp after the treatment. Moreover, the size of the pores tends to increase after plasma treatment. With increasing plasma power (33 % and 100 W), it was found that the membranes were highly damaged (Figure S5). So, the activation conditions on plasma equipment was fixed to the lowest power supply and intensity, before the reaction with NH_2 -PEG-Chol.

Figure 3. AFM images of 99:1 PLA:PVA NMs prepared at 600 rpm and 60 s of time, before and after surface activation with oxygen-plasma at 10 % (30 W of power intensity). (a) Height, (b) Amplitude, (c) Phase and (d) 3D profiles. Before (left) and after (right) plasma treatment.

3.4. PLA functionalization with NH₂-PEG-Cholesterol building block molecules

Cholesterol-functionalised polyethylene glycol with an amine end group (NH₂-PEG-Chol) is a PEG conjugate building block molecule with lipophilic behaviour at one end but with good overall water solubility. This molecule was chosen to improve the interaction of antioxidant molecules across the BM, as the objective of the project is the development of biodegradable synthetic

sensors. The covalent attachment of NH₂-PEG-Chol to the PLA NMs was self-supported in ITO/glass substrates, as can be seen in Scheme 2. This method offered to obtain PLA-PEG-Chol films in only three steps, with the advantage of using few amounts of solvent/water for the product purification. The use of plasma to activate the membrane surface was also proved advantageous, since there was no need of further purification processes. However, the power and time of sample exposition to plasma should be well controlled to avoid the polymer degradation or high roughness, as demonstrated in the previous section. After PLA functionalization, the surface wettability was slight higher of that of PLA ($83.80 \pm 4.20^\circ$), *i.e.* with more hydrophilic WCA ($52.36 \pm 7.68^\circ$). After 10 minutes of water droplet monitoring, the WCA of PLA NMs, as for example, decreased to $47.11 \pm 5.63^\circ$ (Figure S6), as expected, due to the film architecture (nanopores). This behaviour being desirable for the BM sensor device.

SEM analysis was chosen to the evaluation of PLA-functionalised samples (PLA-NHS and PLA-PEG-Chol NMs). The SEM micrographs provided in Figure 4 display the morphology changes obtained on membranes after spincoating and removal of PVA component (Figure 4a), after plasma-EDC/NHS treatment (Figure 4b) and after final PEG-Chol functionalization (Figures 4c-e). The presence of homogenous pores for the membranes prepared by spin-coating PLA:PVA 99:1 composition (1200 rpm for 30s) is evidenced in Figure 4a. Besides, after the plasma-EDC/NHS treatment the pore sizes are maintained (Figure 4b), guaranteeing that the parameters of plasma treatment were optimal for such nanomembranes. As can be seen, after the PEG-Chol functionalization step, it was observed the formation of spherical aggregates on the surface of PLA NMs (Figures 4d-e), which was consistent with the nature of PEG-cholesterol molecule. The presence of polar outer shell and lipophilic core gives rise to the appearance of such morphology. It is crucial to note that PEG-Cholesterol is amphiphilic, featuring two distinct domains: the

hydrophilic PEG fraction and the hydrophobic cholesterol fraction. The latter has a propensity to create hydrophobic microdomains through self-association in water.[44] Some of the PLA pores were slightly damaged by the synthetic route and others were fused together, increasing the pore size of PLA-PEG-Chol almost twice than PLA NMs (246 ± 91 nm and 402 ± 132 nm, for PLA and PLA-PEG-Chol samples, respectively). However, the membrane's pores still maintain the BM stability, without the need for tethers, essentially important to improve fluidity across the film for the further ions and molecules transport. In conclusion, the synthesis and PLA modification by oxygen plasma proved to be efficient to generate the BM from biodegradable and bioresorbable polymers. Further SEM images were taken with the backside of one PLA NMs to ensure that the nanometric films were perforated (Figure S7), which is complementary to the topographical analysis.

Figure 4. SEM images of: (a) PLA NM; (b) PLA-NHS NM; (c-e) PLA-PEG-Chol NM with increasing magnification, showing the presence of bigger pores (some of them damaged by the solvent synthesis approach) and the presence of the building block molecules as aggregates. Scale bars are inserted.

3.5. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy of the PLA and PLA-PEG-Chol NMs supported on ITO electrodes

The molecules of cholesterol play an important role in the structural function of cell membranes. They serve as precursors for the synthesis of various steroid hormones and vitamin D, and imparts stability to the cell membrane. Cholesterol molecules covalently bonded to PEG oligomers actuate as lipophilic and hydrophilic building block units, respectively, which are interesting properties to combine with biodegradable PLA films. Therefore, it is crucial to understand the interface properties of the new biodegradable PLA NMs modified with PEG-cholesterol building block units. In this work, EIS was performed to investigate the interface properties of the synthetic bilayer material. The electrical properties of the PLA-PEG-Chol NMs would play an important role for the membrane transport if the system is implanted *in vivo*, in the future.

Taking into account the different nature and architecture (nanoperforated) of PLA-PEG-Chol biomimetic membranes, our hypothesis that two interfaces coexist (Figure 5) was confirmed by the EIS results (Figure 6). First, we evaluated the ITO/glass substrate without any polymeric film. According to Vivier and co-workers,[45] such electrodes actuate as porous materials where the resistance of the electrolyte (R_s) is negligible and the diffusion process is governed by the charge transport in the electrolyte. Therefore, the most important contribution corresponds to the double-layer capacitance (CPE_{DL}) seen in the Figure 5a. The constant phase elements (CPE) fitted in all cases correspond to the non-ideal capacitances of each interface.[46–48] The R_s was found to be at around 80-160 $\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$, in NaCl solution (0.1 M), depending on the different interfaces of the distinct materials (Table 2). After the deposition of the PLA film and further chemical induced perforation (observed by AFM and SEM, Figures 3 and 4), the transport of the electrolyte still meets the ease diffusion across the membrane pores (R_p and CPE_p). However, a small barrier

resistance contribution from the thin PLA film (R_{PLA}) appears, which film is slightly more hydrophobic than the PEG-Chol building blocks (Figure 5b). As the thickness of the PLA NM films is in the nanometric scale (~ 120 nm, Table 1), the capacitance associated to the pores (CPE_p) and the double layer (CPE_{DL}) contributions are very similar ($2.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ F cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{n-1}$ and $5.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ F cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{n-1}$, respectively) (Table 2). The flatter curve of the semi-circle observed in Figure 6a (see inset image), is related to the film blocking effect on mass transport, which minimizes the capacitive response. Such corroborates to the previous results published by other authors working with ultra-thin films.[29,49]

After the incorporation of PEG-Cholesterol molecules to PLA porous films, the electrical behaviour changed to a more capacitive system (Nyquist plot, Figure 6a) with improved diffusion properties. The pore resistance has reduced to the value of $98 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$, which is advantageous for the objective of the study. This behaviour is supposed to be caused by an enlargement of the pores (Figure 5c) after the action of the plasma treatment, and to the better lipophilic-hydrophilic nature of the BM films if compared to that of PLA. Therefore, the building block molecules do not prevent the passage of ions through the membrane, but it enhances their transport. A high biomimetic membrane resistance was found ($R_{BM}=2.2 \times 10^6 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$), which is one order of magnitude of that of PLA monolayer film. The R_{BM} is similar to that found for other bilayer systems, such as tethered lipid bilayer membranes reported by Junghans and Köper.[50]

Altogether, the study demonstrate that the building block units play an important role respect to mass transfer of ions, which seems to be balanced by the hydrophilicity-hydrophobicity nature of the BM. The EEC elements for each sample are described in Table 2.

Figure 5. Simplified representation of the mechanism for water and NaCl diffusion to the working electrode surface across the BM (on left) and the EEC models (on right) proposed to: (a) ITO/glass substrate; (b) ITO/PLA NMs; and (c) ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol bilayer system. Note that not all the pores perforate the membrane film but are supposed to be deep enough to facilitate the diffusion of the ions. The different EEC elements displayed are: resistances (R) and constant phase elements (CPE), where “S” denotes solution; “DL” corresponds to the double-layer; “p” is related to pores; “PLA” is the biodegradable perforated NM; and “BM” denotes the biomimetic membrane.

Figure 6. (a) Nyquist and (b) Bode plots of ITO/glass substrate, ITO/nanoperforated PLA NM, and ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM in 0.1 M of NaCl solution. Symbols correspond to experimental data, while lines are fitted curves according to EEC displayed in Figure 5.

Table 2. Values of resistances and capacitances, for each sample analysed by EIS in 0.1 M NaCl solution, and obtained after fitting the EEC displayed in Figure 5.

Sample	ITO/glass	ITO/PLA NM	ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM
$R_s(\Omega \text{ cm}^2)$	123	159	80
$R_p(\Omega \text{ cm}^2)$	-	4.6×10^4	98
$CPE_p(\text{F cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{n-1})$	-	2.3×10^{-6}	4.5×10^{-6}
n	-	0.93	0.97
$R_{PLA}(\Omega \text{ cm}^2)$	-	9.3×10^5	-
$R_{BM}(\Omega \text{ cm}^2)$	-	-	2.2×10^6
$CPE_{dl}(\text{F cm}^{-2}\text{s}^{n-1})$	1.0×10^{-5}	5.2×10^{-6}	3.7×10^{-6}
n	0.97	0.69	0.98

3.6. Electrochemical detection of the oxidation behaviour of ascorbic acid and Trolox with PLA-PEG-Chol NMs

Once the existence of different interfaces in the BM was proved and, in particular, the resulting electrical properties of the new function, the membrane interaction with antioxidant molecules was investigated. The choice of vitamin C and a derivative of vitamin E, such as ascorbic acid (AA) and Trolox[®] (Tx), was motivated just due to the envisaged final application of those NMs as implantable biosensor for analytes detection. As known, antioxidants located in both hydrophilic and lipophilic fluids of body (*e.g.*, plasma on blood) act as a defence mechanism against reactive oxygen species (ROS). Thus, the levels of such molecules in biological fluids are relevant to maintain a good human body health and minimize the risk to develop some diseases.

The redox behaviour of such molecules were already studied in previous works by using different electrodes and electrolyte solutions.[51,52] For instance, Sempionatto *et al.* [53] have described the detection of dehydroascorbic acid (*i.e.* the oxidized compound of AA) by fabricating

an epidermal patch sensor for nutrition regulation. They compared an enzymatic amperometric sensor with non-enzymatic sensor and found a good linearity for the SWV response at high concentrations of vitamin C (600 μM , in PBS buffer).

In the present study, the redox mechanism of AA and Trolox under SWV and CV experiments can be also explained in terms of deprotonations, electron transfer reactions and hydration steps (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Major intermediate forms and stable products derived from the chemical and electrochemical reactions of: a) ascorbic acid and b) trolox compounds.

According to the SWV reported in Figure 8, a maximum oxidation peak (E_{ox1}) is obtained from SWV spectra in all systems at about 70-80 mV (vs. Ag|AgCl), due to the rapid deprotonation and

consecutive loss of two electrons from AA molecules (p-AA) into a deprotonated or dehydroascorbic acid species (d-AA) (Figure 7a). In the electrodes without the BM, this process is only governed by the diffusion of the compounds through the ITO/PLA surface. Apparently, the increased current densities indicates no saturation point for this anodic peak, over successive additions of solution aliquots. PLA NM itself maintain the same behaviour and current density values than the supporting electrode (Figure 8a-b). Regarding the potential peak displacement to higher potentials, they are attributed to the decrease pH on the electrolyte solution with enhanced AA concentration. The pH values varied from 6.8 to 4.0, from 0 M to 200 μ M of [AA]. Calibration curves of the mentioned SWV are shown in Figure S8a. More interestingly, after BMs functionalization, a lower oxidation potential peak (E_{ox2}) appeared (Figure 8c-d), involving the electrochemical oxidation of AA molecules into intermediates which can be strongly adsorbed on the PLA-PEG-Chol surface, thus leading to a kinetic and thermodynamic combined mechanism. Contrary to E_{ox1} peak tendency to increase with enhanced AA content, the E_{ox2} decreases. Since oxidation is accompanied by loss of protons (Figure 7a), the higher the concentration of ascorbic acid in the medium, the lower the ease of deprotonation. The E_{ox2} peak could be related to the intermediates that are most stabilized by resonance due to the mobility of charges, such as the oxidized specie AA^* , showed in the Figure 7a. The complete electrochemical mechanism for AA deprotonation and oxidation was evaluated by Tu *et al.* [54], by applying computational simulations, and they explained the existence of stable species as a function of the pKa of the media.

Validation is an essential requirement that ensures the quality and reliability of the results for any analytical application. Thus, calibration curves were carried out with different set of samples with high and low antioxidant concentrations (50 to 200 μ M and 5 to 100 μ M, respectively), to

determine the lower limit of detection (LOD) and the linearity of data (correlation coefficient). As is shown in Figures 8e and 8f, two linear ranges from 0 to 100 μM were obtained for AA, represented as $E_{\text{ox}1}$ and $E_{\text{ox}2}$ peaks, respectively. The LOD was calculated to be 8.12 μM for $E_{\text{ox}1}$ and 11.65 μM for $E_{\text{ox}2}$ based on the Eq. 1, which values are summarized in Table 3. According to the findings shared by Hagel *et al.*,[55] the average concentration of vitamin C found in the plasma samples of a German population consisting of 300 patients was 7.98 mg/L, which corresponds to 45 μM . It was also discovered that patients with a low plasma level, had a vitamin C deficiency (less than 5 mg/L, $\sim 28 \mu\text{M}$), and for a probable most deficient patients (less than 1.5 mg/L, $\sim 8 \mu\text{M}$) were found. Thus, the combination of our polymer electrode with the SWV technique allows detecting vitamin C even in patients with very high deficiency.

Although AA detection displayed some interferences, such as the oxidation peaks displacement due to pH changes, broader and some overlapping between $E_{\text{ox}1}$ and $E_{\text{ox}2}$ at low concentrations, the linearity and repeatability in such antioxidant concentrations range were achieved, demonstrating the good stability of the BM developed here. The CV plots for all samples are displayed in Figure S9, as complementary data for comparison. As can be seen, the $E_{\text{red}1}$ was inappreciable, only a small shoulder of the reduction process was observed for low [AA] (less than 50 μM), demonstrating the high stability of the compound d-AA (Figure 7a) generated.

Figure 8. SWV graphs related to AA detection: (a) ITO/glass substrate, (b) ITO/nanoperforated PLA NM and ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM at high (c) and low concentration (d) of AA, respectively. Calibration curves of ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM at low concentration of AA (d) obtained from E_{ox1} (e) and E_{ox2} (f). Linear regression analysis performed with three independent samples.

The redox mechanism of Trolox are substantially different from that of AA due to the presence of the phenolic group (Figure 7b). The first step is the electron loss. This single electron transfer (Tx^{+*}) is followed by a fast proton-coupled electron transfer to generate the phenoxonium ion (Tx^+). In aqueous-based environment, this carbocation is highly instable and undergoes a rapid

hydrolysis reaction to form the Trolox quinone (TxQ).[56] Another single electron transfer occurs and generates the radical anion compound $\text{TxQ}^{\cdot-}$, highly stabilized in acidic media. Therefore, this intermediate form can be correlated to the highest oxidation potential (E_{ox1}), whereas the most the most instable (Tx^+) can be associated to the E_{ox2} , which decreases with higher Trolox concentrations (Figure 7b). The pH of Trolox solution varied from 6.0 to 5.0 in the water:ethanol solutions (from 5 to 200 μM).

Contrarily to AA molecules, Trolox has much sharper, separated and stable oxidation potential peaks when interacting with the functionalized BM (Figure 9). Once again, no saturation was found for E_{ox1} peak (Figures 9a-d), which represents the direct oxidation of Trolox molecules across the nanoporated film, whereas E_{ox2} decreases with increasing antioxidant concentrations (Figure 9c-d). The linear regression curves of E_{ox1} peak in ITO/glass substrate, ITO/nanoperforated PLA NM and ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM at high concentrations are shown in Figure S8b, while E_{ox1} and E_{ox2} of ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM at low concentrations are represented in Figures 9e-f, respectively. Therefore, after calibration, the LOD for Trolox in PLA-PEG-Chol NM was found to be 3.53 μM and 5.32 μM , with correlation coefficients (R^2) of 0.9777 and 0.9726, respectively, for E_{ox1} and E_{ox2} concentrations ranges. These numbers demonstrate that the BMs have a stronger predilection toward the redox behaviour of such antioxidant compound than AA, with very similar reliability. However, the linearity range for AA, which is from 5 to 100 μM , is higher than the one for Trolox from 5 to 25 μM . Similar to AA experiments, CV assays were also conducted for all samples in the presence of Trolox antioxidant. The results are display in Figure S10 as complementary data for comparison. In PLA-PEG-Chol electrodes, only one oxidation peak is clearly obtained, representing the E_{ox1} , whereas E_{ox2} is hardly detected. Moreover, the CV corresponds to an irreversible electrochemical reaction, *i.e.* the E_{red1} was almost inappreciable.

Thus, SWV approach proved to be more precise and to offer enhanced peak separations, allowing better identification of AA and Trolox electronic transition states, thanks to the interaction of such molecules with the PEG-Chol building block component.

Figure 9. SWV graphs related to Trolox detection of: (a) ITO/glass substrate, (b) ITO/nanoperforated PLA NM and ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM at high (c) and low concentration (d) of Trolox, respectively. Calibration curves of ITO/PLA-PEG-Chol NM at low concentration of Trolox (d) obtained from E_{ox1} (e) and E_{ox2} (f). Linear regression analysis performed with three independent samples.

Table 3. LOD values for AA and Trolox molecules analysed by SWV in aqueous salt solution, as shown in Figures 8e-f and 9e-f, respectively, for several concentrations of AA and Trolox (Tx).

SWV results	E _{ox} (V)	LOD (μM)	[AA]	LOD (μM)	[Tx]
		AA	range (μM)	Trolox	range (μM)
ITO (E _{ox1})	0.70	39.43	50-200	11.06	50-200
PLA (E _{ox1})	0.70	26.61	50-200	20.64	50-200
PLA-PEG-Chol (E _{ox1})	0.70-0.90	8.12	5-100	3.53	5-25
PLA-PEG-Chol (E _{ox2})	0.25-0.30	11.65	5-100	5.32	5-25

It is worth noting that in the CV graphs of AA and Trolox (Figures S9 and S10), a decrease in the peak current and an increase in the distance between oxidation and reduction peaks (shift of Eox1 peak to higher potentials) are evident. Particularly in the Trolox CV graphs (Figure S10) this phenomena occurs as the electrode surface increases its blocked surface ratio: ITO/glass < PLA NM < PLA-PEG-Chol. This phenomenon aligns with the behaviour previously described by Davies *et al.*[57] for partially blocked electrodes.

Table 4 provides a comprehensive performance comparison between the current sensor and several electrochemical sensors reported earlier, specifically for the determination of AA and Trolox. The data presented in this table reveal LOD values comparable to those achieved by other organic-based electrodes. Notably, the PLA-PEG-Chol electrode membrane stands out due to its distinctive composition, being exclusively crafted from biodegradable compounds. This unique

feature underscores its environmentally friendly nature, setting it apart from the conventional materials employed in similar electrochemical sensors.

Table 4. Comparison of analytical performance of the different electrodes for detection of ascorbic acid and Trolox.

Method	Range (μM)	LOD (μM)	Ref
<i>Ascorbic Acid</i>			
CB/PLA	5-20	0.21	[55]
n-MgF/SPE/E μ PAD	0-80	2.44	[58]
PLA/f-MWCNT	200-1000	180	[59]
PLA-PEG-Chol	0-100	8.12	This work
<i>Trolox</i>			
SnS@f-CNF	0.5-26	0.02	[60]
G/PEDOTPSS/SPE	5-30	0.59	[61]
e-PAD/PPE	5-400	1.17	[62]
PLA-PEG-Chol	0-25	3.53	This work

4. Conclusions

The successful route to prepare BMs with biodegradable polymer and lipophilic building block molecules that interacts with antioxidant molecules has been proved. The functionalization of the PLA nanomembranes was achieved in only three steps, being the surface activation with plasma a very promising method, thanks to minimizing the use of organic volatile solvents and no need of

exhaustive purification steps. The synthetic route allows the up-scale production of macrosized films with thickness in the nanometric scale.

Close inspection of the electrochemical results led us to conclude that positive complexation of AA and Trolox molecules with PLA-PEG-Chol films was achieved, when using small doses over the 0 – 100 μM and 0 – 25 μM ranges, respectively, and very low LOD. The well-defined response to such micromolar content of vitamin C and vitamin E derivative determined with SWV technique, indicates the suitability of the BM for practical testing of a prototype biosensor in the future.

Therefore, future efforts will focus on the nanomembrane selectivity and sensitivity to discriminate either hydrophilic or lipophilic antioxidants from biological fluids, such as saliva, sweat and urine, in which much more interfering compounds are involved. This will pave the door for more readily manufactured, better solved non-enzymatic sensors that do not require time-consuming, harsh chemicals and mechanical fabrication procedures.

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Supporting Information. It contains photographs of the macroscopic films, FTIR table with absorption bands, H-NMR spectra, AFM and SEM topography analysis, and, CV results. The supporting file is available free of charge from journal webpage.

Corresponding Authors

*Elaine Armelin (elaine.armelin@upc.edu) and Juan Torras (joan.torras@upc.edu)

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